

Title: Characterizing metabolomic signatures related to coffee and tea consumption and their association with incidence and dynamic progression of type 2 diabetes: A multi-state analysis

Authors: Guzhengyue Zheng, Shanshan Ran, Jingyi Zhang, Zhengmin (Min) Qian, Fei Tian, Hui Shi, Michael Elliott, Maya Tabet, Yin Yang, Hualiang Lin

ORCID IDs: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3643-9408> (Hualiang Lin)

Correspondence Address: No. 74, 2nd Yat-sen Road, Yuexiu District, Guangzhou, Guangdong, China (linhualiang@mail.sysu.edu.cn)

Joint Authorship: N/A

Affiliations: Department of Epidemiology, School of Public Health, Sun Yat-sen University, Guangzhou, China (Guzhengyue Zheng, Shanshan Ran, Jingyi Zhang, Fei Tian, Hui Shi, Yin Yang, Hualiang Lin); School of Medicine, Xizang Minzu University, Xianyang, China (Guzhengyue Zheng); Department of Epidemiology and Biostatistics, College for Public Health & Social Justice, Saint Louis University, Saint Louis, United States of America [Zhengmin (Min) Qian & Michael Elliott]; College of Global Population Health, University of Health Sciences and Pharmacy in Saint Louis, Saint Louis, United States of America (Maya Tabet).

Key words: tea, coffee, metabolomic signatures, type 2 diabetes progression, multi-state regression

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¹ Study investigators, conference presentations, preprint publication information, thanks.

Abstract

Our study aimed to investigate the impact of tea and coffee consumption and related metabolomic signatures on dynamic transitions from diabetes-free status to incident type 2 diabetes (T2D), and subsequently to T2D-related complications and death. We included 438,970 participants in the UK Biobank who were free of diabetes and diabetes complications at baseline. Of these, 212,146 individuals had information on all metabolic biomarkers. We identified tea- and coffee-related metabolomic signatures using elastic net regression models. We examined associations of tea and coffee intake and related metabolomic signatures with the onset and progression of T2D using multi-state regression models. We observed that tea and coffee consumption and related metabolomic signatures were inversely associated with the risk of five T2D transitions. For example, HRs (95% CIs) per SD increase of the tea-related metabolomic signature were 0.87 (0.85, 0.89), 0.97 (0.95, 0.99), 0.91 (0.90, 0.92), 0.92 (0.91, 0.94), and 0.91 (0.90, 0.92) for transitions from diabetes-free state to incident T2D, from diabetes-free state to total death, from incident T2D to T2D complications, from incident T2D to death, and from T2D complications to death. These findings highlight the benefit of tea and coffee intake in reducing the risk of occurrence and progression of T2D.

Keywords: tea, coffee, metabolomic signatures, type 2 diabetes progression, multi-state regression

Introduction

In 2021, 537 million individuals worldwide lived with type 2 diabetes (T2D), and T2D cases are estimated to reach 783 million by 2045 (1). People with T2D face severe complications, including macrovascular disease, microvascular complications, and premature mortality (2). Thus, there is an urgent need to prevent the occurrence of T2D and delay the development of complications.

A healthy diet has played a fundamental role in T2D prevention and complication control (3). Specific dietary components, such as tea and coffee, have been linked to T2D (4, 5), with mixed findings (6, 7). Some studies have demonstrated that tea intake was negatively linked to the risk of T2D (8, 9), while others have not (10). Several epidemiological studies have reported the preventive effects of coffee consumption on the onset and progression of T2D (11-13). Tea is rich in tea polyphenols, and coffee is high in bioactive compounds such as caffeine, phenolics, diterpenes, and chlorogenic acids, which may prevent the onset and progression of T2D through antioxidative, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antiviral, antimutagenic, and thermogenic properties and by promoting metabolism(5, 14). However, previous studies analysing the associations of tea and coffee intake with the onset and progression of T2D have typically only examined disease status (15, 16), and have not examined the progression trajectories of T2D.

In recent years, studies have reported that high-throughput metabolomic techniques can objectively measure the host's metabolic response to dietary intake (17-19). Several epidemiological studies and randomized controlled trials have identified metabolomic signatures related to tea and coffee (20, 21). However, few studies have investigated the associations of metabolomic signatures reflecting tea and coffee intake with T2D-related outcomes (21). In addition, no studies have investigated the associations of metabolomic signatures reflecting tea and coffee intake with the progression trajectories of T2D.

Therefore, we conducted multi-state regression models to examine the effects of tea and coffee consumption, as well as their corresponding metabolomic signatures, on the transitions from a diabetes-free state to incident T2D, subsequently to T2D complications, and finally to death among adults from the UK Biobank.

Methods

Study population

We used data from the UK Biobank, an ongoing prospective cohort study in the United Kingdom (22). The UK Biobank was established during 2006-2010 with over 0.5 million participants aged 37-73 years. Participants in the UK Biobank cohort provided information on socioeconomic characteristics, lifestyle exposures, family history of diseases, dietary intake, plasma sample, and history of medication and disease via physical and biological measurements, verbal interviews, and

questionnaires at baseline (2006-2010) (23).

Among 502,461 participants, we excluded participants with no follow-up (1298 participants), prevalent cases of any types of diabetes or diabetes complications at baseline (59,025 participants), and those with incomplete data on tea and coffee consumption (3168 participants) (Figure S1). Notably, at baseline, prevalent cases of diabetes and diabetes complications were identified in three ways: hospital inpatient and primary care records through the International Classification of Disease, Tenth version (ICD-10) codes, self-reported data, and diabetes-related medication status (24). The final analytic cohort of 438,970 individuals (the primary sample) had comparable baseline characteristics to the 502,461 participants initially recruited to the cohort (Table S1). To identify metabolomic signatures reflecting tea and coffee intake and investigate the associations of metabolomic signatures with the dynamic progression of T2D, we used a subsample of 212,146 participants who had data for all metabolic biomarkers (Figure S1).

Assessment of tea and coffee consumption

Dietary data, including tea and coffee intake, were collected using a food frequency questionnaire (FFQ). Four rounds of FFQ dietary surveys on coffee and tea intake were conducted from 2006 to 2022 (Appendix S1 and Figure S2). Most participants only completed the FFQ survey at baseline. Nevertheless, comparing tea and coffee intake at the second, third, and fourth dietary assessments versus at baseline revealed that most participants who developed T2D during follow-up did not alter their tea and

coffee consumption (Table S2). Therefore, we only used tea and coffee consumption at baseline as dietary exposure. Tea and coffee consumption was considered a continuous variable (cups/day) when identifying their corresponding metabolomic signatures. To determine whether tea and coffee consumption was associated with T2D progression, we classified participants into the following three categories, based on the distribution of tea and coffee intake: tea (<1 cup/day, 1-2 cups/day, and ≥ 3 cups/day) and coffee (<1 cup/day, 1-3 cups/day, and ≥ 4 cups/day).

Metabolomics profiling

Details regarding metabolic biomarker profiling, including plasma sample collection, metabolomics analysis, the multistep processing procedure, and quality control, can be obtained from UK Biobank online resources (25) and have been described previously (26, 27). In short, biomarker data from approximately 275,000 participants at baseline recruitment (2006-2010) and 17,000 participants at repeated assessment (2012-2013) were collected using high-throughput nucleic magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy on Nightingale Health's metabolic biomarker platform in Finland. Of note, approximately 15,500 individuals participated in both a baseline and repeated assessment. A total of 251 metabolic measures, including 168 absolute levels (mmol/L), 81 ratio measures, and two newly derived variables, were quantified per ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) plasma sample (Table S3). These metabolic measures spanned glycolysis related metabolites, amino acids, lipids, lipoproteins (14 subclasses), ketone bodies, fatty acids, fluid balance, and inflammation. Based on

previous studies (21, 28, 29), we included all 251 metabolites in the subsequent elastic net regularized logistic regression models.

Follow-up for outcomes

Follow-up time was counted from the date when participants consented to join the UK Biobank until the date of loss to follow-up, death, or the last follow-up (31 December 2022), whichever came first. In the current study, the outcomes of interest were incident T2D, T2D complications, T2D-specific death, and total death. Outcomes that occurred during follow-up were identified through primary care, hospital admissions, and death registries linked to the UK Biobank (22). We defined the outcomes using the ICD-10 codes (Appendix S2).

Covariates

Data on potential confounders were collected from baseline questionnaires, including age (years, continuous), sex (male/female), ethnicity (White/non-White), residence (urban/rural), income-to-poverty ratio (<1.0/1.0-2.5/2.5-3.9/ \geq 4.0), education attainment (college degree or higher/any school degree/vocational qualifications and other), family history of diabetes (yes/no), alcohol intake (g/week, continuous), smoking status (current/previous/never), physical activity [metabolic equivalent of task (MET) in weekly hours, continuous], dietary supplement (yes/no), body mass index (BMI) (\geq 30 kg/m²/25-29.9 kg/m²/18.5-24.9 kg/m²/ $<$ 18.5 kg/m²), hyperlipidemia (yes/no), and hypertension (yes/no) (Appendix S3).

Statistical analysis

Continuous variables are described as the mean (standard deviation, SD), and categorical variables are presented as the frequency (proportion). Multiple imputation techniques were applied to fill in the missing values for all covariates (30, 31) (Appendix S4). Baseline characteristics are shown by five disease transitions. Spearman's correlation coefficients were used to assess the correlation between tea and coffee consumption and related metabolomic signatures.

The present study included a two-phase analysis: we assessed the associations of tea and coffee consumption with T2D progression in phase I analysis, and we identified metabolomic signatures related to tea and coffee intake and explored their associations with T2D progression in phase II analysis. The identification of metabolomic signatures reflecting tea and coffee intake was conducted through several steps: (1) the biomarker values were *Z* score standardized; (2) metabolites reflecting tea and coffee intake were selected from 251 metabolites, and their corresponding regression coefficients (weights) were obtained using elastic net regularized logistic regression models (Tables S3–S5); and (3) tea- and coffee-related metabolomic signatures were obtained by multiplying the selected metabolite standardized values with the corresponding weights and then summing them together.

We applied multi-state regression models to estimate hazard ratios (HRs) and 95%

confidence intervals (CIs) for the effects of tea and coffee consumption (three categories, with <1 cup/day set as reference group) as well as tea- and coffee-related metabolomic signatures (per SD increment) on T2D progression. The multi-state model is an extension of competing risk survival analysis, allowing simultaneous estimation of the role of certain risk factors on different transition phases (32, 33). In this analysis, the multi-state model consisted of three states (incident T2D, T2D complications, and death). Therefore, participants might contribute to five disease transitions, including the transition from baseline (diabetes-free state) to incident T2D, from baseline to all-cause death, from incident T2D to T2D complications, from incident T2D to T2D-specific death, and from T2D complications to T2D-specific death (Figure 1). Tests for linear trends were conducted by assigning the midpoint value of tea and coffee intake to each of the categories and including the midpoint values in the multi-state regression models as continuous variables.

Based on knowledge of clinical relevance or their relationships with dietary exposures and outcomes (34, 35), we selected a priori potential confounders and conducted two models to assess the associations between tea and coffee intake (as well as their related metabolomic signatures) and five transitions in the T2D trajectory. Model 1 was adjusted for age, sex, ethnicity, education attainment, income-to-poverty ratio, and residence. Model 2 additionally adjusted for alcohol consumption, smoking status, family history of diabetes, physical activity, dietary supplements, hyperlipidemia, hypertension, and BMI, and mutually adjusted for tea and coffee intake (or tea- and

coffee-related metabolomic signatures).

Sensitivity analysis

Several sensitivity analyses were conducted. For the identification of metabolomic signatures, we restricted the analyses to participants who were free of cancer and chronic kidney disease (CKD) and who reported at baseline that they did not often change their dietary habits. For the evaluation of the associations of tea and coffee consumption and related metabolomic signatures with T2D progressions using Model 2, we further: (1) restricted the sample to individuals who were free of cancer and CKD; (2) excluded participants who developed outcomes we interested in the first two years of follow-up, because these case patients might modify their diet during the pre-diagnostic disease phase that preceded enrollment; (3) excluded participants who reported at baseline that they often changed their dietary habits; (4) assessed the associations of tea and coffee consumption and related metabolomic signatures with T2D complications and T2D-associated mortality among individuals with T2D at baseline; (5) controlled for household income (<18,000£, 18,000 – 30,999£, 31,000 – 51,999£, 52,000 – 99,999£, \geq 100,000£) instead of income-to-poverty ratio in multi-state models; (6) controlled for total energy intake (kcal/day, continuous) and intake of sugary drinks (g/day, continuous) in multi-state models, in a sample with 24-hour dietary recall surveys that provided information on sugary drinks and energy intake (n = 190,647) (Appendix S5).

Stratified analyses

To determine whether the associations of tea and coffee consumption, as well as their related metabolomic signatures, with T2D outcomes differed by subgroups, we repeated the multi-state models in Model 2, stratified by age (< 55 and \geq 55 years) and sex.

All analyses were performed in R. The multi-state Markov model was built using the “mstate” package. *P* values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results

Baseline characteristics

Table 1 shows the baseline characteristics of 438,970 participants by disease transitions during follow-up. In this sample, 56.7% were females, the mean (SD) age was 56.0 (8.1) years, 5.1% were non-White, and 15.0% lived in rural areas. Participants who developed disease and progressed to death tended to be older, be males, live in urban areas, have lower income-to-poverty ratio and education attainment, be a former or current smoker, have higher alcohol intake and a higher BMI. Tea and coffee consumption levels were weakly correlated with each other (Spearman correlation coefficient: -0.31, *P*-value = 0.152). Baseline characteristics of the subsample are shown in Table S6. In the subsample, the mean (SD) age was 56.1 (8.1) years, 55.3% were females, 4.5% were non-White, and 14.9% lived in rural areas. The baseline characteristics of individuals who progressed to disease and death

were similar to those of the primary sample.

During a median follow-up of 13.6 years, 12,440 (2.8%) participants developed incident T2D (transition A); 29,865 (6.8%) participants died without experiencing T2D (transition B); 5,162 (41.5%) participants with incident T2D developed T2D complications (transition C); 681 (5.5%) participants with T2D died without developing related complications (transition D); and 873 (16.9%) participants with T2D complications died (transition E) (Figure 1). The five transitions for our subsample are shown in Figure S3.

Associations of tea and coffee intake with T2D progression

Table 2 shows the associations of tea and coffee consumption with the risk of five disease transitions. In general, we observed that higher consumption of tea and coffee was associated with lower risk of five disease transitions. Specifically, in Model 2, compared with participants who drank less than one cup of tea per day, those who drank four or more cups of tea per day had significant protective effects on transitions from diabetes-free state to incident T2D [HR: 0.84 (95% CI: 0.78, 0.91); p for trend < 0.001], from diabetes-free state to total death [0.83 (0.79, 0.87); P for trend < 0.001], from incident T2D to T2D complications [0.86 (0.76, 0.97); P for trend = 0.010], from incident T2D to death [0.63 (0.41, 0.94); P for trend = 0.038], and from T2D complications to death [0.73 (0.52, 0.90); P for trend = 0.012]; compared with participants who drank less than one cup of coffee per day, those who drank three or

more cups of coffee per day had significant protective effects on transitions from diabetes-free state to incident T2D [HR: 0.79 (95% CI: 0.73, 0.84); *P* for trend < 0.001], from diabetes-free state to total death [0.77 (95% CI: 0.73, 0.81); *P* for trend = 0.010, from incident T2D to T2D complications [0.88 (95% CI: 0.77, 0.98); *P* for trend = 0.025], from incident T2D to death [0.76 (0.53, 0.98); *P* for trend = 0.036] and from T2D complications to death [0.79 (0.60, 0.97); *P* for trend = 0.001]. Similar results were observed in Model 1.

Notably, we found threshold effects of tea and coffee intake on transitions from incident T2D to T2D complications, from incident T2D to death, and from T2D complications to death (Table 2). When tea intake was ≤ 3 cups/day (or coffee intake was ≤ 2 cups/day), we did not observe significant associations between tea or coffee intake and these three transitions. Instead, when tea intake was ≥ 4 cups/day or coffee intake was ≥ 3 cups/day, significant protective effects on these three transitions were observed.

Metabolomic signatures reflecting tea and coffee intake

Out of the 251 metabolites we examined, 32 and 38 were significantly associated with consumption of tea and coffee, respectively (Tables S3-S5), with 24 metabolites being associated with both. Both tea- and coffee-related metabolites were primarily lipids and lipoproteins (15 metabolites for tea and 18 for coffee), amino acids (6 metabolites for tea and 6 for coffee), and glycolysis related metabolites (3 metabolites for tea and

4 for coffee). The tea-related metabolomic signature was significantly correlated with tea intake ($r = 0.46$, $P < 0.001$), and the coffee-related metabolomic signature was significantly correlated with coffee intake ($r = 0.48$, $P < 0.001$).

Associations of metabolomic signatures with T2D progression

As shown in Table 3, tea- and coffee-related metabolomic signatures were associated with lower risk of five disease transitions. In Model 2, HRs (95% CIs) per SD increase of the tea related metabolomic signature were 0.872 (0.851, 0.893) for the transition from diabetes-free state to incident T2D, 0.969 (0.954, 0.985) for the transition from diabetes-free state to death, 0.910 (0.904, 0.916) for the transition from incident T2D to T2D complications, 0.921 (0.905, 0.938) for the transition from incident T2D to death, and 0.906 (0.896, 0.915) for the transition from T2D complications to death. HRs (95% CIs) per SD increase of the coffee related metabolomic signature were 0.886 (0.865, 0.906) for the transition from diabetes-free state to incident T2D, 0.940 (0.926, 0.955) for the transition from diabetes-free state to death, 0.908 (0.902, 0.914) for the transition from incident T2D to T2D complications, 0.923 (0.907, 0.940) for the transition from incident T2D to death, and 0.902 (0.893, 0.911) for the transition from T2D complications to death. Similar results were observed in Model 1.

Sensitivity and stratified analyses

The results of sensitivity analyses were consistent with those from primary analyses

(Tables S7 – S20). Stratified analyses by sex and age showed most observed interactions lacked major implications (Tables S21 – S24).

Discussion

We identified 32 and 38 metabolites related to the consumption of tea and coffee, respectively. Both tea- and coffee-related metabolites were primarily lipids and lipoproteins, amino acids, and glycolysis related metabolites. We observed that higher consumption of tea and coffee and the related metabolomic signatures were associated with a lower risk of all five disease transitions, namely from a diabetes-free state to incident T2D, from a diabetes-free state to T2D complications, from incident T2D to T2D complications, from incident T2D to death, and from T2D complications to death.

Comparison with other studies and explanations

We observed that tea consumption was associated with a reduced risk of five stages of T2D progression. Previous studies examining the association of tea intake with the onset and progression of T2D, have typically only examined disease status and have yielded inconsistent results. The EPIC-InterAct case-cohort study, the Health Professionals Follow-Up Study, and the Nurses' Health Study found that regular tea intake has a protective effect on the onset of T2D (36, 37), which was consistent with our results. Ma et al. reported that the consumption of tea had an inverse association with cardiovascular diseases (CVD) outcomes and all-cause mortality among adults

with T2D (38), which supports our findings. However, a double-blind, randomized study among 49 patients with T2D found no significant association between the extract of black and green tea and changes in glycosylated hemoglobin (10). Three possible reasons for the nonsignificant association include the fact that the intervention factor studied was the extract of tea, the limited study time frame of 3 months, and the blinded, placebo-controlled, and randomized study design (10). Nevertheless, despite mixed findings, most studies have shown that tea intake could reduce the risk of the onset and progression of T2D.

We also found that the consumption of coffee was associated with a reduced risk of the five stages of T2D progression. Prior research in this area is in line with our findings. The Nurses' Health Study and the Health Professionals Follow-Up study found that consumption of coffee is inversely associated with incident CVD [HR for the highest versus the lowest intake = 0.82 (95% CI: 0.69, 0.98)] and total death [HR for the highest versus the lowest intake = 0.74 (95% CI: 0.63, 0.86)] among patients with T2D (38). The Korean National Health and Nutrition study showed that coffee intake is inversely associated with the risk of diabetic retinopathy in adults with diabetes (13). Hossein et al. reported that drinking coffee is associated with a reduced risk of mortality in patients with T2D (39).

We found that most of the tea- and coffee-related metabolites were lipoproteins and lipids, amino acids, and glycolysis related metabolites, which was also supported by

previous evidence that tea and coffee can have an effect on lipids and lipoproteins, amino acids, and glycolysis related metabolites (40-42). In addition, we observed that tea- and coffee-related metabolomic signatures were associated with the incidence and progression of T2D. Consistent with our results, a nested case-control study documented that 34 coffee-related plasma metabolites were predominantly lipids and were associated with the risk of T2D (21); another nested case-control study reported an inverse association between the metabolite panel of filtered coffee and the risk of T2D (43). While these studies were limited to examining T2D status, our study focused on five dynamic stages of T2D progression. Further, no study has investigated the associations of tea-related metabolomic signatures with T2D outcomes. Given that 24 of the metabolites associated with coffee intake were also associated with tea intake in the present study, it is not surprising that the corresponding metabolomic signature of tea was associated with T2D outcomes. Future studies are needed to further assess the associations of tea-related metabolomic signatures and T2D risk.

Although associations between tea and coffee intake and T2D-related outcomes have been assessed extensively, associations with T2D dynamic transitions remain unknown. Previous studies analysing the associations of tea and coffee intake with the onset and progression of T2D have typically only examined a single disease outcome. Our study adds to the available evidence by evaluating the effects of tea and coffee intake on the dynamic progression of T2D. Notably, we found that a significantly reduced risk of developing complications from incident T2D and mortality from T2D

or T2D complications among regular tea drinkers of ≥ 4 cups per day and coffee consumers of ≥ 3 cups per day. When limiting the sample to individuals with T2D at baseline, we observed significant inverse associations between the consumption of tea (or coffee) and the risk of disease progression from T2D to its complications, from T2D to mortality, and from T2D complications to mortality. These findings provide further supporting evidence that drinking tea or coffee might decrease the risk of complications occurring among individuals with T2D and fatal events among patients with T2D or T2D complications.

The potential mechanism for the preventive effect of tea consumption on T2D risk is mainly attributed to tea polyphenols, such as catechins, anthocyanins, flavones, and phenolic acids (5). Tea polyphenols may prevent the onset and progression of T2D in three ways: first, tea polyphenol intake can inhibit gluconeogenesis and prevent glucose absorption (44); second, tea polyphenol intake may directly enhance glucose metabolism by improving insulin sensitivity and increasing insulin secretion (45); third, tea polyphenols have lipolytic, antioxidative, anti-inflammatory, and anti-obesity effects, which are important in the aetiology of T2D (14). The beneficial effects of coffee on T2D risk are possibly due to the presence of caffeine, phenolics, chlorogenic acids, trigonelline, diterpenes, melanoidins, and polyphenols. These beneficial bioactive compounds have been suggested to improve lipolysis (46), inhibit gluconeogenesis, delay glucose uptake (47), and reduce systematic inflammation (12) and oxidative stress (48). The abovementioned mechanisms relating to glucose, lipid,

and amino acid metabolism are consistent with our findings that the metabolites associated with tea and coffee are mainly glycolysis-related metabolites, lipoproteins and lipids, and amino acids.

Strengths and limitations

Strengths of this study include the use of the multi-state model, the large population-based cohort with long-term follow-up, detailed information on diet and confounding factors, and on the use of a series of sensitivity analyses to confirm the robustness of our findings.

Nevertheless, our study has several limitations. First, we only used consumption of tea and coffee at baseline as exposure because most participants only completed the FFQ survey at baseline. However, we compared tea and coffee intake at the second, third, and fourth dietary assessments versus at baseline; most participants who developed T2D during follow-up did not alter their tea and coffee consumption. Second, we cannot exclude the possibility of residual confounding given the observational nature of this study. Third, the UK Biobank study participants were mainly White and healthy volunteers. This may limit the generalizability of our results. Fourth, we could not adjust for the total energy consumption in the primary analyses since this information was unavailable from the UK Biobank's FFQ surveys. However, we conducted a sensitivity analysis where we further controlled for total energy intake and consumption of sugary drinks in a sample with 24-hour dietary recall surveys; the

results were consistent with those from the primary analysis. Finally, only approximately 45% UK Biobank participants had general practitioner data, which may lead to a less precise estimate of the risk factor-outcome associations for incident T2D and T2D complications.

Conclusions

In conclusion, our study showed that regular consumption of tea and coffee was associated with a reduced risk of T2D incidence and progression. Metabolomic signatures reflecting tea and coffee intake were associated with T2D progression. These results not only suggest that increasing tea and coffee intake could be beneficial for primary, secondary, and tertiary prevention of T2D but also suggest that measuring metabolites representative of tea and coffee intake might enhance precision in predicting T2D progression.

Author contributions

GZ was responsible for conceptualization, methodology, formal analysis, software, and writing the original draft; ZQ, ME, and MT were responsible for language modification and polishing; FT and HS contributed to methodology and software; SR, JZ, and YY were responsible for data curation; HL worked on conceptualization, data curation, project administration, resources, supervision, and re-drafting. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

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Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts or competing interests that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Ethics approval and consent to participate: The project has approval from the North West Multi-Centre Research Ethics Committee (MREC) (REC reference: 21/NW/0157). Each participant in the UK Biobank provided written informed consent.

Data Availability Statement: The datasets generated and analyzed during the current study are available upon reasonable request to the Access Management System (AMS) through the UK Biobank website (<https://www.ukbiobank.ac.uk/enable-your-research/apply-for-access>).

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Table 1. Baseline characteristics of the participants by disease transitions during follow-up ^a

Characteristics	Baseline	Transition A ^b	Transition B ^c	Transition C ^d	Transition D ^e	Transition E ^f
Number of participants	438,970	12,440	29,865	5162	681	873
Age (years), mean (SD)	56.0 (8.1)	57.9 (7.7)	61.3 (6.6)	59.5 (7.2)	60.5 (6.7)	61.5 (6.3)
Sex, female	248,754 (56.7)	5899 (47.4)	13,740 (46.0)	2295 (44.5)	287 (42.1)	357 (40.9)
Ethnicity, non-white	22,289 (5.1)	1357 (10.9)	869 (2.9)	495 (9.6)	49 (7.2)	41 (4.7)
Residence, rural	65,936 (15.0)	1442 (11.6)	4076 (13.6)	603 (11.7)	86 (12.6)	98 (11.2)
Income-to-poverty ratio						
<1.0	99,338 (22.6)	3677 (29.6)	9471 (31.7)	1709 (33.1)	220 (32.3)	315 (36.1)
1.0-2.4	94,271 (21.5)	2812 (22.6)	7166 (24.0)	1148 (22.2)	162 (23.8)	195 (22.3)
2.5-3.9	101,055 (23.0)	2371 (19.1)	4931 (16.5)	897 (17.4)	111 (16.3)	119 (13.6)
≥4.0	80,536 (18.3)	1332 (10.7)	2810 (9.4)	440 (8.5)	64 (9.4)	51 (5.8)
Missing	63,770 (14.5)	2248 (18.1)	5487 (18.4)	968 (18.8)	124 (18.2)	193 (22.1)

Education attainment

College degree or higher	211,157 (48.1)	4471 (35.9)	11,771 (39.4)	1817 (35.2)	233 (34.2)	258 (29.6)
Any school degree	128,650 (29.3)	3433 (27.6)	7434 (24.9)	1281 (24.8)	180 (26.4)	194 (22.2)
Vocational qualifications and other	91,829 (20.9)	4182 (33.6)	9957 (33.3)	1911 (37.0)	248 (36.4)	392 (44.9)
Missing	7334 (1.7)	354 (2.8)	703 (2.4)	153 (3.0)	20 (2.9)	29 (3.3)

Smoking status

Never	246,300 (56.1)	5964 (47.9)	12,510 (41.9)	2302 (44.6)	276 (40.5)	332 (38.0)
Previous	146,352 (33.3)	4621 (37.1)	11,597 (38.8)	2052 (39.8)	273 (40.1)	353 (40.4)
Current	44,898 (10.2)	1805 (14.5)	5580 (18.7)	785 (15.2)	130 (19.1)	182 (20.8)
Missing	1420 (0.3)	50 (0.4)	178 (0.6)	23 (0.4)	2 (0.3)	6 (0.7)

PA MET (hours/week), mean (SD)	44.7 (40.7)	42.3 (40.6)	44.7 (41.6)	42.4 (41.1)	41.7 (37.2)	41.3 (39.6)
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Alcohol consumption (g/week), mean (SD)	127.0 (120.8)	151.4 (148.2)	154.9 (152.9)	155.9 (155.3)	172.4 (168.3)	161.7 (157.8)
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Family history of diabetes	91,282 (20.8)	4463 (35.9)	5174 (17.3)	1759 (34.1)	209 (30.7)	251 (28.8)
Dietary supplements	205,545 (46.8)	5379 (43.2)	14,550 (48.7)	2295 (44.5)	289 (42.4)	398 (45.6)
BMI (kg/m ²)						
<18.5	2465 (0.6)	18 (0.1)	337 (1.1)	8 (0.2)	4 (0.6)	3 (0.3)
18.5-24.9	94,539 (21.5)	6641 (53.4)	7138 (23.9)	2770 (53.7)	302 (44.3)	443 (50.7)
25-29.9	147,794 (33.7)	1128 (9.1)	9081 (30.4)	467 (9.0)	84 (12.3)	99 (11.3)
≥30	192,188 (43.8)	4545 (36.5)	12,995 (43.5)	1869 (36.2)	287 (42.1)	318 (36.4)
Missing	1984 (0.5)	108 (0.9)	314 (1.1)	48 (0.9)	4 (0.6)	10 (1.1)
Hypertension	186,388 (42.5)	7933 (63.8)	16,683 (55.9)	3546 (68.7)	426 (62.6)	611 (70.0)
Hyperlipidemia	51,630 (11.8)	3007 (24.2)	5397 (18.1)	1465 (28.4)	136 (20.0)	267 (30.6)

^a Values are numbers (percentages) unless stated otherwise.

^b Transition A, diabetes-free participants developed incident T2D.

^c Transition B, diabetes-free participants directly developed death.

^d Transition C, incident T2D patients developed T2D complications.

^e Transition D, incident T2D patients directly developed death.

^f Transition E, participants with T2D complications developed death.

Abbreviations: BMI, body mass index; MET, metabolic equivalent; PA, physical activity; SD, standard deviation; T2D, type 2 diabetes.

Table 2. HRs (95% CIs) of tea and coffee intake with risk of five progressions of T2D using the multi-state model ($n = 438,970$).

Transitions	Tea			Coffee			
	Cases	Model 1 ^a	Model 2 ^b	Transitions	Cases	Model 1 ^a	Model 2 ^b
Baseline → Incident T2D				Baseline → Incident T2D			
<1 cup per day	2072	1.00	1.00	<1 cup per day	3231	1.00	1.00
1-3 cups per day	5078	0.82 (0.78, 0.87)	0.93 (0.86, 1.00)	1-2 cups per day	5316	0.80 (0.77, 0.84)	0.81 (0.76, 0.87)
≥4 cups per day	5290	0.76 (0.72, 0.80)	0.84 (0.78, 0.91)	≥3 cups per day	3893	0.80 (0.75, 0.84)	0.79 (0.73, 0.84)
<i>P</i> for trend		<0.001	<0.001	<i>P</i> for trend		<0.001	<0.001
Baseline → Death				Baseline → Death			
<1 cup per day	4552	1.00	1.00	<1 cup per day	6438	1.00	1.00
1-3 cups per day	11,543	0.81 (0.78, 0.84)	0.83 (0.80, 0.87)	1-2 cups per day	13,364	0.84 (0.81, 0.87)	0.85 (0.82, 0.89)
≥4 cups per day	13,770	0.81 (0.78, 0.84)	0.83 (0.79, 0.87)	≥3 cups per day	10,063	0.84 (0.81, 0.87)	0.77 (0.73, 0.81)
<i>P</i> for trend		<0.001	<0.001	<i>P</i> for trend		0.052	0.010
Incident T2D → T2DCs				Incident T2D → T2DCs			
<1 cup per day	848	1.00	1.00	<1 cup per day	1357	1.00	1.00
1-3 cups per day	2114	0.99 (0.91, 1.08)	1.02 (0.91, 1.14)	1-2 cups per day	2207	0.99 (0.92, 1.06)	0.99 (0.90, 1.09)
≥4 cups per day	2200	0.89 (0.81, 0.98)	0.86 (0.76, 0.97)	≥3 cups per day	1598	0.90 (0.82, 0.98)	0.88 (0.77, 0.98)

<i>P</i> for trend		0.014	0.010	<i>P</i> for trend		0.020	0.025
Incident T2D → Death				Incident T2D → Death			
<1 cup per day	107	1.00	1.00	<1 cup per day	140	1.00	1.00
1-3 cups per day	288	1.07 (0.84, 1.36)	0.98 (0.73, 1.31)	1-2 cups per day	297	0.86 (0.60, 1.13)	0.84 (0.63, 1.06)
≥4 cups per day	286	0.68 (0.46, 0.95)	0.63 (0.41, 0.94)	≥3 cups per day	244	0.75 (0.52, 0.97)	0.76 (0.53, 0.98)
<i>P</i> for trend		0.138	0.038	<i>P</i> for trend		0.005	0.036
T2DCs → Death				T2DCs → Death			
<1 cup per day	163	1.00	1.00	<1 cup per day	197	1.00	1.00
1-3 cups per day	330	0.87 (0.68, 1.06)	0.91 (0.71, 1.11)	1-2 cups per day	358	0.96 (0.78, 1.19)	1.02 (0.82, 1.21)
≥4 cups per day	380	0.72 (0.54, 0.91)	0.73 (0.52, 0.90)	≥3 cups per day	318	0.81 (0.63, 0.98)	0.79 (0.60, 0.97)
<i>P</i> for trend		0.007	0.012	<i>P</i> for trend		<0.001	0.001

^a Model 1 was adjusted for age, sex, ethnicity, income-to-poverty ratio, education attainment, and residence.

^b Model 2 was based on model 1 and additionally adjusted for smoking status, physical activity, alcohol consumption, family history of diabetes, and dietary supplement, hyperlipidemia, hypertension, BMI, and mutually adjusted for tea and coffee.

Abbreviations: CIs, confidence intervals; HRs, hazard ratios; T2D, type 2 diabetes; T2DCs, type 2 diabetes complications.

Table 3. HRs (95% CIs) of tea-related and coffee-related metabolic signature with risk of five progressions of T2D using the multi-state model ($n = 212,146$)^a.

Transitions	Tea-related metabolic signature (per SD increment)		Coffee-related metabolic signature (per SD increment)	
	Model 1 ^b	Model 2 ^c	Model 1 ^b	Model 2 ^c
Baseline → Incident T2D	0.888 (0.872, 0.904)	0.872 (0.851, 0.893)	0.875 (0.860, 0.891)	0.886 (0.865, 0.906)
Baseline → Death	0.991 (0.978, 1.003)	0.969 (0.954, 0.985)	0.972 (0.962, 0.982)	0.940 (0.926, 0.955)
Incident T2D → T2DCs	0.913 (0.908, 0.917)	0.910 (0.904, 0.916)	0.910 (0.905, 0.914)	0.908 (0.902, 0.914)
Incident T2D → Death	0.923 (0.910, 0.936)	0.921 (0.905, 0.938)	0.919 (0.908, 0.929)	0.923 (0.907, 0.940)
T2DCs → Death	0.910 (0.903, 0.918)	0.906 (0.896, 0.915)	0.905 (0.898, 0.912)	0.902 (0.893, 0.911)

^a HRs and 95% CIs of T2D progression risk per standard deviation increment in the metabolic signature.

^b Model 1 was adjusted for age, sex, ethnicity, income-to-poverty ratio, education attainment, and residence.

^c Model 2 was based on model 1 and additionally adjusted for smoking status, physical activity, alcohol consumption, family history of diabetes, and dietary supplement, hyperlipidemia, hypertension, BMI, and mutually adjusted for tea-related metabolic signature and coffee-related metabolic signature.

Abbreviations: CIs, confidence intervals; HRs, hazard ratios; SD, standard deviation; T2D, type 2 diabetes; T2DCs, type 2 diabetes complications.

Figure titles

Figure 1 Transitions from diabetes-free status to incident T2D, T2D complications, and all-cause death. Diabetes complications included diabetic eye diseases, diabetic kidney diseases, diabetic neuropathy diseases, cardiovascular diseases, peripheral vascular diseases, and metabolic events. State-specific number of events was reported in boxes, and the transition-specific number of events and percentages (within brackets) were reported on arrows.

Abbreviations: T2D, type 2 diabetes.